
EFFICIENT USE OF THE AVAILABLE WATER RESOURCES IN UZBEKISTAN

Egamberdiev Otabek, Murtazaeva Fayyoza, Olloiniyozov Sardor

PhD students of “Scientific Research Institute of Irrigation Water Problems”

Abstract: In the article, it is calculated how much land can be irrigated by using water-saving technologies in the irrigated land areas. As a result, water resources are sufficient, and it was mentioned that it is possible to irrigate additional land or increase the number of irrigations.

Key words: drip irrigation, water saving, irrigation, water quantity, water shortage, water consumption.

Introduction. In recent years, consistent reforms have been implemented on effective use of land and water resources, improvement of the water resources management system, modernization and development of water management facilities. At the same time, due to global climate change, the growth of the population and economic sectors, and their demand for water is increasing year by year, the shortage of water resources is increasing year by year. Due to the lack of precipitation during the growing season of plants in the territory of Uzbekistan, maintaining soil moisture is carried out only through irrigation measures. This situation requires not only responsibility, but also spending a lot of money. The irrigated land areas of Uzbekistan differ sharply from other countries in terms of the importance of the water management system in the processes of cultivating these areas and producing high yields, as well as in terms of the amount of funds allocated to this sector by the state [2, 3]. In the republic, in 2020-2030, it is necessary to provide the population and all sectors of the economy with water, to improve the reclamation of irrigated lands, to widely introduce market principles and mechanisms, digital technologies to water management, and to ensure the reliable operation of water management facilities. The development of the concept aimed at increasing the efficiency of the use of land and water resources is the result of reforms in the field of water management [1]. Especially in the conditions of today's water shortage, further expansion of the introduction of water-saving irrigation technologies in the cultivation of agricultural crops and the implementation of the issues of attracting foreign investments and grants to this field are considered urgent tasks. It is known that climate change can lead to an increase in the water shortage in Uzbekistan, an increase in the duration and frequency of droughts, such as in 2000, 2008, 2011, 2014 and 2018. There is a possibility that serious difficulties will arise to meet the economy's need for water resources [4].

Methods

Comparative comparison, logical and abstract thinking methods were used in the research process. The research was carried out by analyzing long-term data on irrigated lands and irrigation networks of Kashkadarya region in Uzbekistan.

Research results

Kashkadarya region is a region within the Republic of Uzbekistan and was established on November 1, 1924. In the south-west of the republic, in the Kashkadarya basin, on the western edge of the Pamir-Aloy mountain range, between the Amudaryova-Zarafshan rivers, Hisar and Zarafshan mountain ranges. It borders Bukhara to the northwest and Surkhandarya regions to the southeast, the Republic of Turkmenistan to the southwest and west, the Republic of Tajikistan and Samarkand region to the east. The area is 28.6 thousand km². There are 667.6 thousand hectares of cultivated land in Kashkadarya region, of which 418.7 thousand hectares are irrigated land [5].

According to the Ministry of Water Resources, if we analyze the amount of water received in Kashkadarya region in the last ten years, it is on average 10.47% of the total amount of water received in the Uzbekistan (Table 1) [6].

Table 1.

**Average amount of water received in Kashkadarya in many years,
million cubic meters**

Territory name	Years										More than average yearly
	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	
Kashkadarya reg.	5856.4	5460.0	5659.4	5893.2	6396.8	4830.0	5447.6	5641.2	4602.8	4508.6	5429.6
By republic in % of total:	10.85	10.54	10.26	10.80	10.85	9.47	10.09	11.01	10.54	10.18	10.47

Diagram 1. Percent share of Kashkadarya region receiving perennial water

So, the received water differs little compared to the total for the Republic. There are 418.7 thousand hectares of irrigated land in Kashkadarya region. The average value of the amount of water received in many years is 5429.6 million cubic meters (diagram 2). From this,

$(5429,6/418,7) = 12967,7$ The average water flow per cubic meter.

Diagram 2. Average amount of water received in Kashkadarya region in many years

According to the results of the calculation, there is actually a water shortage. Even with the most efficient use of water, water does not reach many areas. The main reason is that there is a huge loss in irrigation networks from the source to the irrigation field. In this regard, in 2020-2030, it is necessary to provide the population

and all sectors of the economy with water, improve the reclamation of irrigated lands, widely introduce market principles and mechanisms and digital technologies to water management, and increase the number of water management facilities. It is specifically mentioned in the Concept [1] aimed at ensuring reliable operation and increasing the efficiency of land and water resources use. We also calculate whether the total available water is enough or not enough.

Amount of water consumption of plants during normal or direct irrigation:

- cotton - 6000-9000 m³/ha;
- wheat - 3000-4000 m³/ha;
- corn - 5000-6500 m³/ha [7].

If we calculate from the given value, on average, 6000 m³/ha of water consumption will be used. At least 50% of water will be saved if irrigation works are carried out in Kashkadarya region using fully water-saving technologies. So,

$(50\% \cdot 6000) / 100 = 3000$ m³/ha is average.

According to the results of the analysis, an average of 12967.7 m³/ha is spent on 1 hectare of Kashkadarya region.

Based on calculations

$(3000 / 12967.7) \cdot 100 = 23\%$ to corresponds,

in practice, 418.7 thousand hectares of land are irrigated. Then,

$100\% - 23\% = 77\%$ average water savings.

As a result, it will be possible to irrigate an additional 1391.1 thousand hectares of land, or 3.3 times more than the existing irrigated land.

Conclusion

In conclusion, if all irrigated agricultural lands are irrigated using water-saving technologies, it will be possible not only to save water, but also to irrigate additional lands or increase the number of irrigations. An increase in the number of irrigations leads to an increase in productivity. If productivity increases, output increases. The introduction of "Smart and digital water management" technology in scientific research institutes will further develop. As a result, it will be possible to further develop the economy.

References:

1. Decree No. PF-6024 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan On approval of the concept of water management development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030. July 10, 2020.
2. Salahiddinov A.T., Ashirova O.A. Water resources basin planning and management Training manual. Tashkent. “TIAME” NRU 2020. - 216 p.

3. Ibragimova M. M., Mukhamadov Q. M. Prospects for the development of rational and efficient use of land and water resources in the republic //SCIENCE AND INNOVATION international scientific journal// ISSN: 2181-3337, 2022 No. 2

4. Shokhojaeva Z.S. Foreign experiences in the use of water-saving technologies and their application to the agriculture of our country //Innovative educational, natural and social sciences// 2022

5. Information from the National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan (2000-2005).

6. Information from the Ministry of Water Management of the Republic of Uzbekistan

7. Khamidov M.Kh., Shukurlaev K.I., Mamataliev A.B. Agricultural hydrotechnical melioration, T.: Sharq, 2009: -380 p.